

Near surface Air Temperature and Carbon dioxide in Indian Sundarbans: A Time Series Analysis

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Abstract

The atmospheric carbon dioxide was measured at 18 m above the ground with a Non-Dispersive Infra-Red (NDIR) gas analyzer fitted with a thermometer during 1984 – 2016 at Sagar Island in western part of Indian Sundarbans. The atmospheric carbon dioxide exhibited the lowest value of 384.98 ppm (during premonsoon 1984) to 401.22 ppm (during postmonsoon 2016). The highest peak of air temperature during premonsoon 2009 may be attributed to Aila (a super-cyclone that passed across the lower Gangetic delta during premonsoon 2009). We find overall increasing trends of these two variables, which strongly confirm the rapid rate of industrialization and urbanization in this mangrove dominated ecosystem. The change of land use pattern (due to unplanned expansion of shrimp culture farm at the cost of natural mangroves) is also a strong reason for the local scale rise of atmospheric carbon dioxide as well as air temperature. Massive plantation of mangroves may be an effective road map to get rid of the situation.

Keywords: Carbon Dioxide, Near Surface Air Temperature, Sagar Island.

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1. Introduction

The phenomenon of climate change has shaken the whole world and has brought political leaders, scientists, common people and business classes on a common platform. Everybody wants a solution and for this many terminologies like adaptation, mitigation etc. have come in the limelight. However, before any type of treatment, it is essential to know the root causes of the disease and then only one can be confident about the curing steps. The causes of climate change can be broadly categorized into natural and anthropogenic. The natural factors include phenomenon like continental drift, several astronomical cycles, variation in solar energy output (due to magnetic storms in the sun) and volcanic activity [1]. The anthropogenic factors are human induced changes of the environment.

Over the past few decades it has become increasingly apparent that human actions are changing atmospheric composition, triggering the events of climate change. Anthropogenic factors are altering the world's climate by increasing the atmospheric concentrations of gases, which amplify the natural "greenhouse effect" [2] that makes the planet earth habitable.

According to the 4th assessment report (2007) of the Inter-Governmental Panel on Climate Change (IPCC) one of the most important observed effects includes the rise of global average surface temperature by approximately 0.65°C over the last 50 years (IPCC, 2007). [3] As we continue to change atmospheric composition, climatologist forecast further warning during the coming century and beyond. This is a projection of the rise of global mean surface temperature by 1.1-6.4°C depending partly on future trends in energy use [4].

Coastal and estuarine areas are most vulnerable to climate change because of events like sea level rise, unnatural depression etc. The destruction of blue carbon sink in recent decades may be one of the important factors for the local level rise of carbon dioxide. [1, 5-12]

Expansion of shrimp farm and tourism units coupled with modernization of ports and harbors in coastal zone and river mouths have also changed the area occupied by blue carbon which otherwise could be a major sink of carbon dioxide (Fig. 1).

Figure 1. Modern ports and harbor are built at the cost of blue carbon patches. [13]

On the basis of this background, the present paper aims to explore the trend of near surface air temperature and atmospheric carbon dioxide over more than three decades in the largest island of Indian Sundarbans, the Sagar Island located at the confluence of Bay of Bengal and the River Hooghly (Fig. 2).

Materials and methods

The atmospheric carbon dioxide concentration at Sagar Island was measured at 18 meter above the ground on the campus of Youth Hostel at Sagar South (21° 38' 51.55" N and 88° 02' 20.97" E), with a non-dispersive infrared gas analyzer (LI6262, LI-COR Inc., USA). We installed and air intake at 1 meter above the roof of the building. A diaphragm pump was used to draw air through a ¼ inch Teflon tube at a rate of 10 litre per minutes with most of the air being vented off. The step of removal of water vapour was performed and the air sample was introduced into a sample cell of the NDIR analyzer, and the output voltage of the NDIR analyzer was integrated at five-minute interval. The analyzer was calibrated every four hours by successively introducing four calibrated working gases (340, 380, 410 and 450 ppm carbon dioxide in dry air) into the NDIR analyzer cell for five minutes each. The experiment was performed in every year (1984 – 2016) in three fixed months namely May (premonsoon), September (monsoon) and December (postmonsoon).

Figure 2. Sagar Island (large triangular shaped, red colored): Our experimental site.

Results

The air temperature in the present study site ranged from 28.4°C (during postmonsoon 1984) to 36.1°C (during premonsoon 2009). The atmospheric carbon dioxide exhibited the lowest value of 384.98 ppm (during premonsoon 1984) to 405.09 ppm (during postmonsoon 2016). The high peak of air temperature during premonsoon 2009 may be attributed to Aila (a super-cyclone that passed across the lower Gangetic delta during May 2009). We find overall increasing trends of these two variables since the last three decades. The present study also exhibited unique seasonal trends of both these variables. The near surface air temperature followed the order premonsoon > monsoon > postmonsoon, while the sequence for

atmospheric carbon dioxide was postmonsoon > premonsoon > monsoon. The temporal variation of carbon dioxide (Fig. 3) followed the global trend (Fig. 4).

Discussion

Carbon dioxide molecules provide the initial greenhouse heating needed to maintain water vapour concentrations. When carbon dioxide concentrations drop, Earth cools, some water vapour falls out of the atmosphere, and the greenhouse warming caused by water vapour drops. Likewise, when carbon dioxide concentrations rise, air temperatures go up, and more water vapour evaporates into the atmosphere, which then amplifies greenhouse heating.

Figure 3. Temporal variation of carbon dioxide in our study site.

Figure 4. Seasonal variation of atmospheric carbon dioxide. [14]

So while carbon dioxide contributes less to the overall greenhouse effect than water vapour, scientists have found that carbon dioxide is the gas that sets the temperature. Carbon dioxide controls the amount of water vapour in the atmosphere and thus the magnitude of the greenhouse effect.

Climate records reconstructed from bubbles of ancient air trapped in ice-core samples going back 420,000 years show a very strong co-relation between temperature and atmospheric carbon dioxide. In the present study area strong correlations exist between near surface air temperature and atmospheric carbon dioxide in all the seasons ($r = 0.8674$; $p < 0.01$ in premonsoon; $r = 0.8998$; $p < 0.01$ in monsoon and $r = 0.9098$; $p < 0.01$ in postmonsoon). The rises of air temperature and carbon dioxide have significant adverse impact on the estuarine ecosystem. The magnitude of possible change in an estuary depends on its geographic location and on future carbon emissions. Climate processes impact the physical, chemical and ecological processes of estuaries in different ways. Importantly the future impact from these processes will not be equally distributed, and the relative impacts will depend on the extent to which these climate drivers vary at regional and local scales and on the adaptability of the various estuarine environment and components to these changes. The present station (Sagar Island) located at the confluence of the Hooghly estuary and Bay of Bengal is surrounded by mangrove vegetation with the presence of some 34 species of true mangrove flora. These mangroves are important sink of carbon. [5-12, 15-20] which may be a plausible cause of relatively low rate carbon dioxide rise compared to the global average.

The results show that both coastal and mangrove wetland ecosystems are significant carbon pools compared to other terrestrial ecosystems and hence demand immediate conservation through their proper management coupled with site-specific mass scale plantation.

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